

Saving energy using RQ-based dynamic controlled atmosphere storage of blueberry fruit

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ABSTRACT

Current high energy prices, but not in the least global warming force us to consume less energy and to decrease our carbon footprint. Cold storage of fruit uses a lot of energy but is needed to maintain produce quality and availability for the consumer. A fair amount of the needed cooling energy is used to compensate the heat of respiration of the stored product. Cold storage temperatures lower metabolic activity of stored product and so decreases the produced heat of respiration. Respiration is further decreased by applying, on top of the cooling, controlled atmosphere (CA) by applying a storage atmosphere with low oxygen concentration and a somewhat elevated carbon dioxide concentration. With dynamic control atmosphere storage (DCA) even lower oxygen levels and so lower respiration heat production can be achieved by progressively lowering the oxygen levels and at the same time measuring the respiration quotient (RQ) of the stored fruit until RQ-values higher than one signal fermentation and the oxygen level is increased again. This changing oxygen level during storage results in the lowest possible production of heat while maintaining product quality. The aim of this research is to evaluate the effect of RQ-DCA storage of blueberry fruit on energy use for storage and on produce quality during storage and subsequent shelf life. Blueberries were stored for 6 weeks in regular air, two CA conditions and two DCA conditions. Firmness, total soluble solids content and total titratable acidity were measured right after storage and after a shelf life of seven days. RQ-DCA stored blueberries were firmer and retained their acidity better compared to others. Consumers preferred RQ-DCA stored berries because of better firmness, less collapsed berries, and a fresher look. About 10% less energy was needed for DCA compared to CA storage for two months.

Keywords: Refrigeration, Carbon Dioxide, Compressors, COP, Evaporators, Energy Efficiency

1. INTRODUCTION

Highbush blueberry (*Vaccinium corymbosum* L.) has become a popular fruit over the last few years (Yahia, 2009). This because of their taste and appearance and because of their health promoting characteristics (Chen et al., 2015; Duarte et al., 2009; Wang et al., 2017).

The climate in Western-Europe does not support the production of blueberries throughout the whole years. In the months before and after the possible growing season for Western European countries, blueberry supply depends on import from production sites in warmer climates, often outside the EU. A possibility to prolong the availability of Belgian grown blueberries on the market is by proper storage of the berries. As blueberries are prone to decay and rapid spoilage, it is necessary to develop effective storage technologies in order to retain quality of blueberries as long as possible. Storing instead of importing from faraway places result in a lower carbon footprint as well as was shown by Goosens et al. (2019) for apples.

Optimal conditions include a low temperature (0.5 °C to 2 °C), lowered O₂ levels and increased CO₂ levels.

To prolong the storage time of blueberries, new storage methods are introduced with the goal to store blueberries (and other fruit) in an optimal way, taking into account the variability and dynamic behaviour of the stored fruit. As the stored fruit is still living it will respire substrates to sustain its metabolism. The consumption of substrates goes along with a loss in food reserves and depletion of volatile compounds such as malic and citric acids, which can lead to a loss in taste quality (Kader and Saltveit, 2003). Thus, if the respiration rate can be reduced, fruit quality can be kept at a higher level for a longer period (Kader and Saltveit, 2003).

The traditional way to store horticultural products and preserve their quality is in a modified atmosphere, where the applied gas conditions are different than that of normal air (Yahia, 2009). Mostly, O₂ levels are lowered and CO₂ levels are increased, leading to a lower respiration and also an inhibition of oxidative reactions and a lower microbial growth (Yahia, 2009). Several storage techniques have been developed, of which controlled atmosphere (CA) storage is the most used today. Lately, several new techniques like dynamic controlled atmosphere (DCA) have been introduced. These techniques measure a certain bio response of the fruit to low O₂ stress and alter the storage conditions based on the values of the measured response (Bessemans et al., 2016). CA in contrast, is a static method with applied conditions as close as possible to optimal storage conditions. CA storage is usually carried out in a closed cold room with decreased O₂ and increased CO₂ levels in combination with a low temperature (Hoehn et al., 2009). By applying these adjusted conditions, the goal is to lower the metabolism of the fruit and to maintain higher quality. During storage, the goal is to keep the metabolic rate of the fruit as low as possible. The lowest respiration rate can be found at the anaerobic compensation point (ACP), so if fruit can be stored at an O₂ level as close as possible or even at the ACP, the storage time of the fruit can be extended (Bessemans et al., 2016; Dilley, 2010). The ACP of harvested fruit does not only depend on the type of commodity but also varies with picking date, season and origin of the fruit (Bessemans et al., 2016). Also, it is reasonable to expect that the metabolism of a living product is dynamical and thus not constant throughout the whole storage period (Prange et al., 2005). Therefore, during CA storage, a safe margin above the ACP is applied to ensure no fermentation takes place, avoiding unwanted off-flavours and other storage disorders (Fonseca et al., 2002; Geigenberger, 2003; Kader and Saltveit, 2003). However, above the ACP the respiration rate rises quickly with increasing O₂ concentrations, thus meaning a faster senescence of the stored product. (Bessemans et al., 2016). A method of storing the fruit closer by the ACP oxygen level is dynamic controlled atmosphere (DCA). During DCA storage, the lowest oxygen limit (LOL) at which the fruit can be kept without developing storage disorders due to fermentation is actively searched by adapting the O₂ levels as a function of a measured biological response of the fruit material to low oxygen levels (Zanella, 2003).

The general principle of a DCA storage system is the following: A bio-response is measured at regular time intervals and depending on the result, the O₂ concentration inside the storage room is adapted. If low oxygen stress is detected, the O₂ concentration in the room is increased until the relief of low oxygen stress. Otherwise, the O₂ concentration is further lowered (Hoehn et al., 2009). This way, it can be assured that the fruit material is stored under the lowest O₂ concentration possible (Bessemans et al., 2018). Different methods of DCA have been developed throughout the years of which ethanol based DCA (DCS), DCA based on chlorophyll fluorescence (DCF) and RQ based DCA (RQ-DCA) are the most investigated technologies (Hoehn et al., 2009; Prange et al., 2005; Weber et al., 2015).

In this work, we investigate the applicability of RQ-DCA for storage of blueberries by comparing post-storage quality of blueberry fruit stored under RQ-based DCA and conventional CA storage, immediately after storage and after 7 days of shelf life at 7 °C. Main quality attributes such as firmness, soluble solids content and titratable acidity will be assessed as well as the occurrence of disorders. Consumer perception of stored blueberry fruit stored will be assessed. Determining blueberry respiration rates will enable calculation and comparison of the energy use for the different storage modes.

2. MAIN SECTION

2.1. Materials and methods

'Liberty' highbush blueberry fruit were harvested 1st of August in Meeuwen-Gruitrode and transported to the lab. Hundred and ten punnets were randomised and divided in 5 groups of 20 punnets and 2 groups of 5 punnets. Each group of 20 punnets was stored for 6 weeks at 0,5 °C with one of 5 different storage conditions: Regular air (21 kPa O₂, 0 kPa CO₂), CA (5 kPa O₂, 5 kPa CO₂), CA (5 kPa O₂, 10 kPa CO₂), and two DCA storage methods. Both DCA methods are respiration quotient (RQ) based. Details can be found in Bessemans et al. (2016). In short RQ is determined by taking the ratio of measured differences of CO₂ and O₂ concentrations in the closed of storage compartment over a period of about 4 hours. O₂ concentration was lowered with a step size of 0.1 kPa if RQ was lower than 2.0 and increased by 0.2 kPa otherwise. In RQ-DCA-S O₂ concentration varied and CO₂ was kept at 5 kPa. In RQ-DCA-D O₂ and CO₂ both varied in a constant ratio.

One group of 5 punnets was used to assess fruit quality at harvest. The other group of 5 punnets was subjected to a simulated shelf life of 7 days at 7 °C before assessing fruit quality. From each stored group of 20 punnets 5 were randomly chosen to assess fruit quality right after storage. The other 15 punnets were subjected to a simulated shelf life of 7 days at 7 °C before assessing fruit quality and doing a consumer tests.

Soluble solid content (SSC) was assessed by measuring the refractive index of blueberry juice. The tested blueberries were squeezed at room temperature (23 °C) and the juice was collected. The blueberry juice was then placed on the measuring prism of a digital refractometer (Atago, PR101, Japan). The results of the measured SSC content of the blueberries were presented in °Brix (grams of sucrose dissolved in 100 g solution).

Total titratable acidity was quantified using a potentiometric titration (Metrohm 702 SM Titrino, Switzerland) with NaOH (0.1 mol L⁻¹). To prepare the sample, blueberries were put in a juice extractor to separate the juice from the pulp. In order to better separate the juice, a filter cloth was used. Because of the high acidity of blueberry juice, the sample first need to be diluted. For each test, 1 mL of blueberry juice was used and was further diluted with deionized water to 50 mL. After extracting and diluting the blueberry juice, a magnetic stirrer was added, and an end point titration was carried out. The acidity is expressed as the amount of NaOH (0.1 mol L⁻¹) needed to obtain a pH of 8.1.

The firmness of the blueberries was assessed with a Magness-Taylor pressure test using an automated penetrometer (TA-XTPlus Texture Analyser: Stable Micro Systems, UK). The test was repeated for 100 blueberries of each storage type and shelf lifetime. In this destructive test, a circular flat plate with a diameter of 75 mm was used to compress the blueberries at a speed of 1 mm s⁻¹. The blueberries were kept in place using a small cylindrical cup. The firmness was expressed as the maximal force needed to compress the blueberries for 1 mm.

For mold and number of collapsed berries, the number of berries that showed the disorder were manually sorted and the total mass of blueberries was measured for each disorder. The disorders were expressed as a percentage of the total mass of a punnet.

For each assessment of the quality attributes a sample size of 100 fruit was used (20 berries from 5 punnets). A one-way anova and Tukey multiple comparison test was carried out to determine significant differences between storage methods using JMP®Pro 14 (SAS, USA).

A triangle test was organized to assess whether 19 consumers would taste a difference. Afterwards, consumers were asked to rank punnets from high to low willingness to buy.

Respiration rates were determined at harvest using jars of 1.1 L that were filled with ± 375 g of blueberries and closed. For each applied condition, three jars (repetitions) each having an inflow and an outflow valve were connected in series to a gas mixing panel that supplied the desired gas conditions. The jars were flushed at the desired gas conditions for a period of 12 h. After the flushing period, the jars were closed airtight and the gas composition and pressure in each jar was measured at time intervals, with the length of the intervals depending on the temperature. At 0.5 °C, measurements were carried out with an interval of 12 h, at 10 °C

the measurements had an interval of 3 h and at 20 °C, measurements were carried out each hour. The gas composition inside the jar was measured using a portable gas analyser (Checkmate II Headspace Analyser, PBI Dansensor, Denmark), which had an accuracy of $\pm 0.1\%$ for the oxygen reading and an accuracy of $\pm 0.5\%$ for the carbon dioxide reading. The internal pressure of the jars was measured with a calibrated pressure sensor (DPI 142, GE Druck, Germany) with an accuracy of ± 0.1 hPa. The blueberry density was determined using the Archimedes principle measuring the berries underwater weight. The average berry density had a value of $1028.01 \text{ kg}\cdot\text{m}^{-3}$ with a standard deviation $\pm 16.89 \text{ kg}\cdot\text{m}^{-3}$. Oxygen consumption rate and carbon dioxide production rate were calculated from the concentration differences of respectively oxygen and carbon dioxide in the free volume in the jars using the ideal gas law and expressed in $\text{nmol}\cdot\text{kg}^{-1}\cdot\text{s}^{-1}$. Oxygen consumption rate and carbon dioxide production rate were modelled using Michaelis-Menten kinetics with O_2 as the limiting substrate and CO_2 as an uncompetitive inhibitor (Hertog et al., 1998).

$$r_{\text{O}_2} = \frac{V_{m,\text{O}_2}[\text{O}_2]}{K_{m,\text{O}_2} + [\text{O}_2] \left(1 + \frac{[\text{CO}_2]}{K_{mu}}\right)} \quad \text{Eq. (1)}$$

Carbon dioxide production was modelled as the sum of CO_2 produced by aerobic respiration and fermentation which was inhibited by oxygen (Hertog et al., 1998).

$$r_{\text{CO}_2} = q_{r,ox}r_{\text{O}_2} + \frac{V_{m,\text{CO}_2}}{\left(1 + \frac{[\text{O}_2]}{K_{mc}}\right)} \quad \text{Eq. (2)}$$

Eq. (1) and (2) were fitted together to the measured data using the non-linear least squares fit procedure lsqnonlin (The Math Works, Inc. MATLAB. Version 2022b) for each used temperature separately.

2.2. Respiration rates and DCA storage conditions realised

The respiration model used with uncompetitive inhibition of CO_2 (Hertog et al., 1998) fitted the data well. The model Eq. (1) and (2) were fitted on the respiration data gathered at 0.5, 10 and 20°C respectively. The resulting parameter values are given in Table 1 and were comparable with those found by Cameron et al. (1994).

Table 1. Respiration parameter values with 95% confidence intervals for Eq. (1) and (2) at 0.5, 10 and 20°C

parameter	0.5 °C	10 °C	20 °C
V_{m,O_2} ($\text{nmol}\cdot\text{kg}^{-1}\cdot\text{s}^{-1}$)	52.7 ± 5.6	115 ± 14	830 ± 240
K_{m,O_2} (kPa)	2.88 ± 0.66	2.07 ± 0.57	7.5 ± 2.9
K_{mu} (kPa)	55 ± 55	63 ± 73	9.0 ± 5.7
V_{m,CO_2} ($\text{nmol}\cdot\text{kg}^{-1}\cdot\text{s}^{-1}$)	18.3 ± 2.5	72.0 ± 5.1	286 ± 26
K_{mc} (kPa)	0.72 ± 0.42	0.44 ± 0.17	0.34 ± 0.14
$q_{r,ox}$ (-)	0.502 ± 0.051	0.784 ± 0.052	0.916 ± 0.016

Oxygen consumption rate and carbon dioxide production rate were shown in Figure 1 in relation to O_2 and temperature. As no inhibition effect of CO_2 was observed as K_{mu} was rather high and not significant at lower temperatures only, the respiration results at 0 kPa CO_2 were shown. Temperature had the most profound effect on O_2 consumption and CO_2 production rate as both increase by a 10-fold between 0.5 and 20 °C. From 5 kPa O_2 and lower both O_2 consumption rate and CO_2 production rate starts to decrease. While O_2 consumption rate decrease to zero at 0 kPa O_2 , CO_2 production rates reached a minimum value around 0.75 kPa O_2 . This minimum is called the anaerobic compensation point (APC) at which aerobic CO_2 production and fermentative CO_2 production are equal. Storage conditions with O_2 concentrations lower than the APC will favour unwanted fermentation metabolism and need to be avoided. However, storing between commonly applied 5 kPa O_2 and the APC allows for safely decreasing fruit metabolism and respiration resulting in retaining better quality and producing less respiration heat.

Figure 1: Oxygen consumption rate (circles) and carbon dioxide production rate (triangles) and fitted model (Eq. 1 and 2) in relation to oxygen concentration at 3 temperatures

Storage conditions in regular air and regular CA were considered constant. However, in the two DCA storage conditions O_2 concentrations dynamically changed as can be seen in Figure 2. In the first week of storage O_2 and CO_2 concentration were kept the same as in regular CA. After one week the O_2 concentration was lowered in DCA conditions according to the measured RQ values. In the RQ-DCA-D CO_2 condition the CO_2 was kept in constant ratio with O_2 (left pane) while in RQ-DCA-S CO_2 concentration was kept constant at 5 kPa (right pane).

Figure 2: Realised oxygen and carbon dioxide concentrations in DCA storage conditions (left scale) together with measured RQ-values (circles, right scale)

In both cases O_2 concentration decrease to very low values without resulting in RQ-values of more than 2. It was decided to limit the O_2 to minimum 0.5 kPa after 3 weeks of storage which is already past the ACP to avoid possible fermentative damage of the fruit. The RQ threshold of 2 was based on an earlier study of Bessemans et al. (2016), as no earlier research on this type of RQ-DCA for blueberries was done, the same algorithm developed by Bessemans et al. (2016) for RQ-DCA storage of 'Granny Smith' apple fruit was used. It is thus possible that during storage of blueberries, no RQ values were found that are as high as the values measured during RQ-DCA storage of apple fruit. This is because the ACP, which is the point of O_2 concentrations that was searched for during RQ-DCA storage, was at a lower O_2 level for blueberries than for apples, which means that CO_2 production because of fermentation is still rather low at the O_2 levels reached in the storage experiment here.

2.3. Effect of storage techniques on blueberry quality

Several quality parameters were measured after storage and subsequent self-life simulation. The results of firmness, total titratable acidity, percentage collapsed berries and berries with mold are shown in Figure 3. Soluble solid content (data not shown) of blueberries showed no differences between storage methods at a

shelf life of 0 days. After the shelf-life period of 7 days, small significant differences were found in the SSC content. There were also no significant differences between shelf lifetimes. The observations on the SSC content of blueberries after harvest and after a storage period of six weeks are in line with the observation of Duarte et al., (2009). They assumed that the SSC content during storage remained close to constant because of the fact that ripening stops when the fruit is picked (non-climacteric behaviour). This hypothesis is however not validated, as more and more evidence is found that the distinction between climacteric and non-climacteric fruit is not as clear as first thought (Paul et al., 2012).

Figure 3: Quality attributes firmness, total titratable acidity, percentage collapsed berries and berries with mold after storage and subsequent self-life simulation of 7 days. Bars with the same letter per shelf lifetime were not significantly different at a 95% confidence level.

Blueberry firmness after storage did not show differences between the storage methods at a shelf lifetime of 0 days (Figure 2, upper left pane). The firmness of blueberries from RQ-DCA-D and RQ-DCA-S was found to be significantly higher than the firmness of other methods after 7 days of shelf life. This can be a motivation to argue that the fruit stored under RQ-DCA control remained at a lower metabolic rate after storage, leading to a longer possible period that berries are accepted by consumers based on quality. Comparing the results of firmness for the different shelf lifetimes, it can be seen that after a shelf lifetime of 7 days, the firmness had increased for the blueberries after harvest and for the two RQ-DCA storage methods. A reason for this remarkable rise in firmness after 7 days of shelf life could be assigned to the measuring method. Maybe the berries do not get really firmer but toughen somewhat which appears as if they were firmer. Any way the RQ-DCA stored berries behave similar to the ones at harvest in the shelf life simulation appearing fresher than the ones stored in different ways.

The results for titratable acidity presented in right upper pane of Figure 2 show that the titratable acidity of blueberries was lower for regular air storage and CA at 5 kPa O₂ and 5 kPa CO₂ compared to the other storage methods at a shelf lifetime of 0 days. After 7 days of shelf life, the titratable acidity of the blueberries from CA at 5 kPa O₂ and 5 kPa CO₂ were significantly lower than the acidity of blueberries after harvest and after storage in the two RQ-DCA methods. The acid depletion during storage can be explained by the respiration metabolism of fruits. If high acid depletion is observed, it can be assumed that the aerobic respiration rate is high. This is because measured acids like malic acid are intermediate components in the respiration cycle

(Bessemans, 2018). Based the experimental results on titratable acidity, it can be concluded that regular air storage and CA at 5 kPa O₂ and 5 kPa CO₂ were less efficient in reducing the respiration rate, probably because of the combination of higher O₂ levels (21 kPa for regular air and 5 kPa for CA) and the relatively low CO₂ levels (0 kPa for regular air and 5 kPa for CA).

The analysis on the number of collapsed berries showed large increases after 7 days of shelf life for most storage methods (Figure 3, lower left pane). The reasoning might be that the berries were kept at a high relative humidity around 95% for six weeks and were then placed in a cool room with a lower relative humidity and a higher temperature. This caused movement of water out of the blueberries, leading to shrivelling, and collapsing of berries. Berries stored in CA showed up to 1/3 collapsed fruit. This would mean a giant loss in commercial value. It is important to define the factors influencing this disorder and minimize their impact after storage. Although not significant both RQ-DCA storage methods resulted in less collapsed berries compared to the CA stored ones. The assessment of molds after storage and after 7 days of shelf life showed that after 6 weeks of storage and 0 days of shelf life, only a small amount of blueberries were infected by mold (Figure 3, lower right pane). Regular air storage was the only storage method which showed a significant difference in infected berries compared to harvest. The reason that regular air storage had a higher percentage of infected berries can be due to the fact that this storage type is the only storage with very low CO₂ levels, and as explained by Harb and Streif, (2004), elevated CO₂ levels during storage are effective in reducing the growth of mold. During the shelf life time, temperature was higher than during storage and CO₂ levels were much lower for most storage types, which can be the cause of the resulting rise in the percentage of infected blueberries for RQ-DCA-S storage and CA 5 kPa CO₂ storage.

A triangle test was carried out after 7 days of shelf-life. No significant differences were tasted between CA and DCA stored berries (Table 2). However, 80% of the consumers ranked RQ-DCA stored berries the highest because they were more firm, less collapsed and had a fresher look.

Table 2. Results of the triangle test carried out among 19 consumers

Test	Correct answers	Significance (alpha = 0.05)
RQ-DCA-D vs. CA 10 kPa CO ₂	6/19	No
RQ-DCA-S vs. CA 5 kPa CO ₂	7/19	No

2.4. Energy use during storage

To compare energy use for cold storage of blueberries either stored in CA at 5 kPa O₂ or using RQ-DCA-S a cool room with a volume of 170 m³ and walls of 15 cm of PUR isolation material was assumed. As these rooms are commonly part of a cooling complex of several rooms it was assumed that only half of the walls are exposed to a mean temperature difference of 15 °C resulting in wall loses of 230 W. Storage temperature is set at 0.5 °C which implies defrosting of the evaporator will be needed. The needed power to do this is estimated for the room at 85 W on average. Ventilators (10 W/m³) are assumed to run one fourth of the time resulting in an average power dissipation of 430 W in the room.

The room was loaded with 19.2 ton of berries consuming 35 O₂ nmol.kg⁻¹.s⁻¹ at 0.5 °C as can be seen in Figure 1. If we assume all the oxygen consumed is used to combust glucose aerobically this results in 480 kJ.mol⁻¹ O₂ or 0.0168 W.kg⁻¹ fruit. This means the berries in the room produce 323 W respiration heat when storing in CA at 5 kPa O₂. The total amount of heat that needs to be removed from the room is then 1072 W. If RQ-DCA is applied and O₂ concentrations of about 1 kPa are reached the heat of respiration will decrease by at least 50% which result in about 15% lower total heat that needs to be removed from the room. When the loading of the room is also taken into account and tangible heat of the fruit needs to be removed the gain between CA and DCA remains about 10% for a total storage period of 2 months.

3. CONCLUSIONS

The developed respiration model fitted well on the respiration measurements of Liberty blueberries. CO₂ was found to have a negligible inhibition effect on respiration, especially at low storage temperatures. The ACP

was found to be about 0.75 giving plenty of room to apply RQ-DCA reaching much lower O₂ concentrations as in CA for blueberries is commonly applied. Blueberries were successfully stored under RQ-DCA for 6 weeks. The quality of blueberries was assessed right after storage and after a shelf life simulation of 7 days. RQ-DCA stored blueberries were firmer compared to others. Also, consumers preferred RQ-DCA stored berries because they were more firm, less collapsed and had a fresher look. RQ-DCA storage showed to be successful in maintaining quality at a high level in terms of firmness, SSC content, titratable acidity and the prevention of storage disorders while needing about 10% less energy for cooling compared to normal CA storage.

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NOMENCLATURE

$[CO_2]$	CO ₂ concentration (kPa)	$q_{r,ox}$	Quotient of respiration at high O ₂ concentration
K_{m,O_2}	Michaelis-Menten constant (kPa)	r_{CO_2}	CO ₂ production rate (nmol.kg ⁻¹ .s ⁻¹)
K_{mu}	Uncompetitive Inhibition constant for CO ₂ (kPa)	r_{O_2}	O ₂ consumption rate (nmol.kg ⁻¹ .s ⁻¹)
K_{mc}	Inhibition constant of fermentation by O ₂ (kPa)	V_{m,CO_2}	Maximal CO ₂ production rate (nmol.kg ⁻¹ .s ⁻¹)
$[O_2]$	O ₂ concentration (kPa)	V_{m,O_2}	Maximal O ₂ consumption rate (nmol.kg ⁻¹ .s ⁻¹)

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